

L U M I AI Factory

LUMI AI Factory Service Center

Empowering Europe's AI Ecosystem

D4.3

Inference service documentation

EuroHPC
Joint Undertaking

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Lead Authors	Juha Hulkkonen, Tomáš Martinovič
Contributors	Pauliina Somerkoski, Emma Hintsala, Jan Martinovič, Juho Keränen
Peer Reviewers	Abdulrahman Azab, Heidi Laine, Katja Mankinen
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Glossary of Terms

Item	Description
Aitta	AI Inference service created in CSC
LumiLingo	Chatbot for Nordic languages created as demonstration application on top of Aitta
LAIFS	LUMI AI Factory Service Center
LLM	Large Language Model
API	Application Programming Interface
REST API	Representational State Transfer Application Programming Interface
Web UI	Web browser User Interface

Executive Summary

LUMI AI Factory's objectives are advancing the development of AI solutions, including offerings like inference service. We expect to see fast-paced growth in computational needs in this area.

This document describes two inference platforms: Aitta and EXA4MIND. Aitta inference platform is developed by CSC, and EXA4MIND developed by the EXA4MIND project consortium (IT4I and METU). The inference services will be provided by LUMI AI Factory.

Inference refers to the process of using an AI model to generate predictions, produce outputs or perform specific tasks based on new input data.

Inference enables real-world applications of Large Language Models (LLMs) and other AI models, allowing users to interact with the model by providing prompts — text inputs that guide the model's responses.

Aitta inference platform is a service to host AI models on supercomputers. With Aitta, you can interact with LLMs efficiently using simple API (Application Programming Interface) calls or simple Web UI (Web browser User Interface). Users will be able to run their self-trained models, use curated portfolio of models. Easy integration to existing model repositories will be provided.

EXA4MIND inference service is developed on efficient leveraging of HPC resources in a project initiative that is building a platform for extreme data (i.e. data that is at the upper or lower limits of expectations that should be accepted by the system), enabling advanced analytics on supercomputers. EXA4MIND inference service solution complements the Aitta inference service with the main difference in the task queue implementation. This opens the possibility for further Aitta extensions and optimization based on the incoming requirements.

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1. Aitta in General

1.1 Introduction to Aitta

Aitta is a general purpose scalable service component to host AI models on a supercomputer. Aitta is offered for LUMI AI Factory Service Center customers to run their AI models in a reliable and powerful computing system safely in Finland, while harnessing powers of energy efficient supercomputers.

Aitta offers a set of curated models via an easy-to-use modern web interface and API endpoints with its own Python library for programmatic usage. The fundamental development idea behind Aitta is that users can run arbitrary models with any type of data they need for their research and development purposes. Aitta saves users from having to set up the servers, or from buying cloud service capacity from third parties. Aitta offers a user-friendly experience, allowing users to focus on their primary tasks and objectives.

AI inference platform Aitta is currently in development stage, originally created to complement CSC's growing AI service portfolio. With LUMI AI Factory the service is to be offered for a wider variety of international use cases and users. CSC offers a variety of computing services, including HPC capacity, scientific support, and training materials, for development of cutting edge AI models, including generative models. Aitta complements the services with providing suitable environments for running heavy AI models.

At the moment Aitta is heavily focused on Large Language Models (LLMs) and our current set of available models includes Nordic language models Poro, Viking, GPT-SW3, FinGPT with modern chat interface.

1.2 Value

Aitta can be seen as a part of commitment for efficient and sustainable use of resources by offering scalability to computing resources and making supercomputers more multi-purpose instruments. Computing resources used for training can be also used for inferencing the models. Running AI models may require substantial computational power, which Aitta uses efficiently by allocating resources on demand. Resources are allocated automatically and freed after a certain period of time.

Aitta will offer various backends to ensure effective use of resources: cloud and container cloud for running small experimental models quickly, national supercomputers and LUMI and LUMI AI for largest and heaviest workloads.

1.3 Future work

In the future, a feature to upload self-trained models will be developed. With help of other MLOps solutions planned to be developed in LUMI AI Factory, users can deploy their models into Aitta. Additionally, the curated portfolio of models, that now consists of LLM models, will be developed further. Access key management will be improved greatly to allow users to integrate Aitta into their

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own services. Currently Aitta development has been concentrating more on use via API, so Aitta has only a basic user interface, that will be developed further to be more user-friendly.

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2. How to use Aitta

Aitta can be used via web user interface or REST API. REST API (Representational State Transfer Application Programming Interface) is a common web service interface.

Aitta has a simple web UI, see [Aitta's webpage](#). The current Web UI is made mainly for testing and development purposes. The WebUI is currently also used to get the access key for programmatic use.

Aitta makes models and inference tasks available via REST API. Aitta REST API is also OpenAI compatible. [AITTA API reference documentation](#) documents the API in detail describing endpoints, parameters, and responses. To be able to use this API, users need to log in to Aitta's webpage to create API keys for access.

A Python client to be used with Aitta API is also developed. This client for programmatic use is published to [PyPi repository](#). With just a few lines of code, one can utilize this client to e.g. integrate and work with LLMs via the Aitta API.

While its development is ongoing and uploading custom models is not yet available, Aitta already provides models for users to explore through the web UI and API endpoints using Python libraries `aitta-client` and `openai`. In the near future, it will also be possible to create embeddings (numerical representations of real-world objects) of the data using Aitta.

2.1 Training Materials

Introduction to Aitta -training is online and available via the [Noppe service](#). Noppe is CSC's service for learning and course purposes, offering web applications for working with data and programming. Noppe supports Jupyter and RStudio based applications.

The training materials are currently located and will be maintained in a [Github repository](#). In need of using instructions with private computer, the material sources can be downloaded from Github.

3. Aitta Inference Service Technical Description

3.1 Aitta Inference Service Technical Description

The system is designed with a modern, modular architecture that supports scalability, maintainability, and efficient resource usage. It follows a microservices approach, allowing individual components to be developed, deployed, and scaled independently.

Users interact with the system through a web-based user interface and a REST API, both of which provide access to powerful machine learning capabilities. At its core, the system manages computational workloads through a task queue and job orchestration engine, enabling asynchronous processing of inference tasks and integration with external systems.

The system is deployed in a cloud-native environment called Rahti, which is a container orchestration service at CSC. This platform provides the necessary tools for automated deployment, scaling, monitoring, and high availability of services. The infrastructure layer is backed by OpenStack based cloud computing platform called Pouta, which is an IaaS (Infrastructure-as-a-service) cloud service at CSC. Pouta enables flexible and scalable resource provisioning by using virtual machines.

High-performance compute jobs are dispatched to HPC resources using the [HEAppE middleware](#) developed by IT4I, which allows seamless job scheduling and execution via Slurm. Slurm (Simple Linux Utility for Resource Management) is an open-source job scheduler used in high-performance computing (HPC) environments to manage and allocate computational resources across a cluster of computers. HEAppE integration is a key for efficiently running large-scale generative models that demand substantial computing power.

Models can run in various backends depending on the need

- EuroHPC supercomputer LUMI and LUMI AI
- National supercomputer Mahti
- IaaS cloud Pouta
- Container cloud Rahti

A high-level overview of the system architecture is illustrated in the figure below.

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Figure 1 AittA architecture.

3.1.1 Web user interface (FastAPI & Gradio)

The web user interface serves as the access point for users to interact with the machine learning models. It is particularly important for applications like chatbots, where a responsive and intuitive interface significantly enhances the user experience.

The interface is built using [FastAPI](#), a modern web framework that supports both the backend logic and API functionality. For generating the web pages dynamically, [Jinja2](#) templating engine is used, which enables us to create flexible, data-driven HTML views.

To make the model interaction more user-friendly and accessible, UI integrates [Gradio](#) — a Python library designed for building simple yet powerful user interfaces for machine learning applications. Gradio allows quick creation of interactive components like input boxes, sliders, or chat windows, depending on the use case.

The frontend itself is built using standard web technologies: HTML, CSS, and JavaScript. This ensures broad compatibility and a clean, efficient user experience across different browsers and devices.

3.1.2 AittA Backend Service API

At the core of the system is the API — the central component responsible for managing and orchestrating the entire machine learning inference workflow. It acts as the backbone that connects various services, coordinates tasks, and ensures everything runs smoothly from request to response.

API is built using the FastAPI framework and it is designed for performance, scalability, and ease of integration in mind. It can support multiple types of clients, including the web interface and Aitta Python client, which enables programmatic access and seamless integration into other platforms and workflows.

The backend service API plays a key role in several tasks like:

- **Task and Worker Management:** It coordinates the lifecycle of model inference tasks, manages worker availability, and ensures efficient resource utilization.
- **Authentication and Security:** It handles authentication and access control, integrating securely with authentication systems.
- **System Integration:** It connects to external services including:
 - **Celery** and **Redis** for distributed task queue management,
 - **MongoDB** for storing and retrieving model metadata,
 - **HEAppE** for dispatching and managing jobs on high-performance computing clusters.

This modular design ensures that the API is not only capable of serving immediate user needs, but also adaptable for future expansion and integration with new tools and infrastructure.

3.1.3 Task and Job Management (Celery & Redis)

To efficiently handle the processing of machine learning requests, the system uses a dedicated task and job management layer. This ensures that inference tasks — which can range from quick predictions to complex computations — are processed reliably and at scale.

The system uses [Celery](#) in combination with [Redis](#) to manage this layer:

- Redis acts as the message broker — it receives incoming requests and places them into a queue.
- Celery picks up these tasks from the queue, assigns them to available workers, and monitors their progress from start to finish.

This architecture allows the system to manage large volumes of requests without slowing down the system itself. Tasks that require longer processing time are handled asynchronously in the background, ensuring that users get a responsive interface without waiting for jobs to complete.

By decoupling the task management to its own service, this enables:

- Scalability — tasks can be distributed across multiple workers
- Reliability — task states and results are tracked and stored
- Efficiency — resources are allocated only when needed

Overall, this setup is essential to ensure that the system can support multiple users, diverse models, and computationally intensive jobs — all in parallel.

3.1.4 Model Metadata (MongoB)

To keep track of the machine learning models available in the system, [MongoDB](#) is used as a metadata database. This database stores essential information about each model.

This metadata allows the API to understand what each model can do and how it should be used.

Using a separate database for model metadata gives flexibility:

- New models can be easily added, update existing ones, or retire outdated versions
- Changes to metadata can be made without interrupting running jobs or redeploying the system
- The system remains extensible and adaptable as new features emerge

By keeping model information structured and centralized, it is ensured that the system remains organized, maintainable, and future proof.

3.1.5 High-End Application Execution Middleware (HEAppE)

To support the execution of large-scale machine learning models — especially resource-intensive generative models — the system integrates with [HEAppE](#), a middleware platform that connects the system to high-performance computing (HPC) resources.

HEAppE allows the system to:

- Dispatch jobs to powerful compute clusters
- Leverage [Slurm](#), the industry-standard workload manager, to schedule and manage those jobs within the HPC system
- Monitor and control resources, ensuring that models are only loaded when needed and efficiently released when idle

This integration enables the system to scale beyond what standard cloud or on-premise environments typically offer. By offloading the heaviest workloads to HPC, we can ensure performance, reliability, and cost-efficiency — especially when working with large models that demand significant computational power.

In practice, this means users can access powerful ML models through a simple interface, while the complexity of managing the infrastructure is handled automatically behind the scenes.

3.1.6 Authentication

Access to the platform is governed by a centralized authentication system built on [OpenID Connect](#), with user identity verification currently based on organizational LDAP directories. This allows internal users to seamlessly log in and access services through the frontend or programmatically via the API. The overall authentication and authorization model is designed to support a wide range of use cases, including:

- Identification of individual users and their project affiliations
- Interactive token-based access for usage through the Python client or other automated tools

As we continue to expand the system, the access control model is enhanced to support:

- Scoped access to models and computational resources, based on user identity and project membership
- Machine-to-machine authentication, allowing clients to act on behalf of users or projects securely

- Support for both company-internal users and external collaborators (e.g., EU projects)
- A flexible authorization system where model access is restricted to allowed project scopes or users
- Clean separation between authentication logic and API-level authorization, ensuring that access control at the API level remains straightforward and token-based

The architecture is intended to accommodate project-specific requirements, including the ability to integrate with external identity providers and define custom access scopes. In such cases, access tokens are expected to carry the necessary information (e.g., scopes, project identity) in a standardized and verifiable way, enabling the API to remain authentication-agnostic.

This approach ensures that access to sensitive compute resources and models can be securely controlled, while still enabling collaborative and extensible usage patterns.

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4. EXA4MIND inference server

Figure 2 EXA4MIND inference service.

4.1 Introduction

In EXA4MIND we are building a platform for extreme data that enables advanced data analytics on supercomputers and automated data management. Within this project, we are also developing an inference server focused on efficient leveraging of HPC resources. This server uses a combination of FastAPI, HEAppE middleware, and ZeroMQ to enable seamless information exchange with high-performance computing centers through an intuitive interface for inference. This solution complements the Aitta inference server with the main difference in the task queue implementation. Where Aitta uses Celery and Redis on the OpenShift, the EXA4MIND solution uses distributed workers on HPC with custom communication based on ZeroMQ.

4.2 Architecture

4.2.1 Web user interface (FastAPI)

The entry point to the inference server is the web interface created by FastAPI, a simple interface which allows user to write queries for the LLMs and returns models outputs in simple textbox. Cookies will be used to track user session and requests. These are foreseen to be necessary for making sure users will get response in case of job failure, whether it will be information about the failure, or automatic restart of the query.

4.2.2 High-End Application Execution Middleware (HEAppE)

The usage of HEAppE serves the same purpose as in Aitta. The HEAppE will create a SSH tunnel to the ZeroMQ server on the compute job so the FastAPI server can then send queries leveraging this SSH tunnel. The main difference in these solutions is the position of the task queue which is described later in section 4. **Error! Reference source not found..**

4.2.3 Instances and deployed models DB

Scaling is focused on the HPC job sides through adding jobs with HEAppE. For keeping track of the individual HPC jobs, there is a DB which stores two main things: the compute jobs created by HEAppE and related metadata, and the deployed models on these compute jobs. The second item is necessary so we know which models are already available, or whether the users would have to load a new model.

4.2.4 Task queue and scheduling

Each compute job will have a process that acts as a task queue and load balancer using various strategies such as round-robin. There can be multiple AI models deployed in the worker processes (using either multiple single-GPU models or multi-GPU models deployed on one or more compute nodes), with communication between the workers and the main process handled by ZeroMQ.

4.2.5 Logs

For each compute job there will be logs created containing information about user queries, responses, and AI model state. These are mainly used for developers to debug any errors in the server operation.

4.3 Future work

There are multiple features that we would like to add in the future. Among these we are considering adding retrieval augmented generation ([RAG](#)) support, persistence of queues on the compute job to allow restarts in case of failures during the query execution, adding chat history to the user interface, and making the solution more general by allowing different models besides LLMs, such as image generation, audio generation, etc.

